

THE EFFECT OF MORAL-AESTHETIC EDUCATION IN FOREIGN
LANGUAGE CLASSES OF STUDENTS OF TECHNICAL HIGHER
EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: The article reveals the scientific and practical basis of the possibilities of aesthetic education for students of a technical higher education institution through the medium of a foreign language. We believe that the opportunities and conditions that provide students with aesthetic education with the help of a foreign language are a set of measures aimed at the educational qualities of students. At the same time, the content of educational activities in a foreign language includes targeted practice as a permanent component. However, in our environment there is no need for such a practice of communicating in a natural environment and in a foreign language.

KEY WORDS: technical university, foreign language, conditions, aesthetic education, education, improvement

INTRODUCTION: The essence of the personality is extremely refined. Therefore, by analyzing the creative aspect of personal activity, its essence and structure, and increasing the creative aspect of education, we have determined the logical approach to the formation of highly ethical education. The correct solution to this critical issue from a scientific and pedagogical point of view requires taking into account one more important aspect. It is also a difference in the moral, intellectual, aesthetic, and social development of the student. This difference is

primarily related to the age of the person. Before closing this issue in detail, it is the most important vital problem for the youth, the youth, and the generation that will come to the world after the old man. That's why the issue of education is an eternal problem that worries the leaders and thinkers of the nation.

METHODS. The great medieval scientist Abu Payhan Muhammad ibn Ahmad al-Biruni [5] in his book "Memorials of the Past" gave a lot of necessary information about human life. The scientist expressed his opinion on the social structure of people and the length of their lives. Abu Payhan Beruni [5] in his book "India", "Mineralogy" explained the causes of human longevity in connection with biological and genetic factors.

The great thinker scientist, our poet A.Navoi[9] expressed his views on the morals, manners, attitude towards people, spirituality, creativity, and abilities of a mature and mature person in the works "Khazayinul Maoniy", "Mahbub-ul Qulub". In general, it is very worthwhile to study our past history in a comprehensive way.

Many scientists have applied their own principles of stratification of the age group and the research of the age-group interaction. Therefore, a person does not incubate a generality of his own. But this generality should be covered by the external strength and ability of the person as a typical person. A person's individual rights can be assigned to a specific group. The natural source of an individual trait is known as a trait, which is called a genotype in scientific language.

RESULTS. The principle of critical selection of the material content of the English language is based on the fact that the material that is suitable for the development of the worldview of the student is chosen. The effectiveness of the training in the teaching process is clearly increased in the method used because the material selected for the training is important, but also how this material is presented to the student. In the moral and aesthetic training of the student, there are three types of exercises, such as reading a literary text, reading a newspaper article of a problematic nature, playing with the floor on the table, adding a hint to the development of communication, discussion-argument, and meeting-conference.

For example International Student Forum in England. (International Student Forum in England.) The task of the student is to improve the moral-aesthetic education of students on the basis of modern mobility: the student should enter into a relationship with the students of a foreign country, demonstrating his moral-aesthetic education on the basis of dialogue and debate.

The principle of science is reflected in the fact that the information provided in the chapter is scientifically organized, well-informed and meaningful, and researched. In it, it is necessary to provide a conscious attitude of the student to the teaching and learning process, and the student should be able to determine the task set before him, understand the context and method used for ethical and ecstatic learning, and be able to evaluate the knowledge and skills independently.

The principle of activity is a combination of speech activity and thinking. This can be explained by the following considerations:

- 1) the practical activity of the student is always related to the mental activity that directs him;
- 2) mental activity is related to the interest of the student in the field of educational practice;
- 3) improvement of the moral and ecstatic education of the student in the process of assimilation of a foreign language;
- 4) when the material in the educational process is prepared in connection with independent work, the student's activity increases.

DISCUSSION. The reserve of the educational process can be used in accordance with the purpose by combining the teaching of the student's domestic demand with moral-aesthetic training, improving the management of his foreign demand. The availability, assessment and optimality of educational goals and solutions in the context of the development procedure for managing the process of foreign language and moral-aesthetic training of students through foreign languages were discussed. Essentially, when defining the goals of the management program, it analyzes the current situation, analyzes alternative solutions, and

evaluates and designs the activity of students in order to determine the optimality in terms of time and effort spent by the participants of the educational system. An alternative to a scientific research paper involves the selection and evaluation of a different perspective on the subject being studied.

As a foreign language teacher of a higher education student, he performs a variety of tasks, including collecting data and assessing the student's situation, improving the student's moral-ethical attitude and attitude to learning, improving the student's ability to work with the student, and providing a critical approach to problem-solving.

The search task is carried out in connection with the goal of learning and learning another object and the way to give personal importance to the task, that is, in connection with the search for a new way of education.

The study guide helps students to understand the practical and developmental importance of teaching foreign languages. The task of education is related to the understanding of the intended educational goal in learning basic needs. Organizational work is directly related to the activity of organizing the work of the teacher and the student and determining the individual activity of the student.

An important aspect of the improvement of the thesis is the scientific accuracy of the subject, accuracy, conciseness, comprehensiveness and agreement of the recommendation. The success of teaching foreign languages depends to a large extent on the psychological skills of the teacher and the ability to use innovations in the student's work.

The need to know about the life, creativity and culture of the people of the country where the language is being studied is very strong. It is possible to use modern texts, as well as modern poems and songs, to create the words and thoughts of the modern language, and to use them as a guide. This is the basis for making these opinions. Such material fulfils the general educational function of learning the basic requirement.

Ethical-esthetic teaching in foreign language textbooks can be carried out in two directions: secondly, the content of the educational material, secondly, the third and third method of teaching and learning. Our goal is to find the basis for the improvement of moral and aesthetic education in the field of education of students and to offer a suitable and appropriate way in our view.

The main content of mathematics for education is presented in textbooks and textbooks, as well as the topic of oral speech can be clearly expressed in texts to improve listening and reading comprehension, as well as through exercises designed to improve language skills. Pay special attention to the semantic enrichment of each sentence. Textual materials create endless opportunities for moral, ideological, practical, labour, ecstatic and intellectual education. However, reading and understanding alone will not be enough. It is not important for the student to study the book connected to the source, but it is important for the student to know how reliable the source is, the reliability, and the ability to read the fiction, so that the student not only learns the source but also knows the methods and methods of working with it. Therefore, the second direction of the implementation of moral-ecstatic training in the Khobi language class includes the use of such a teaching method that adds the most important to the implementation of the task.

In life, a person requires the creative application of acquired knowledge, skills and competence, that is, the ability to apply knowledge and competence in a new situation. It is a three-fold educational task of learning to think, observe, draw conclusions, and solve logical problems. Thus, working on a text with moral and ecstatic meaning in foreign languages is not limited to reading and understanding. After reading the text, students should be given a cognitive task that will allow them to read the text, express their opinion about the process expressed in the text and their response to the event, justify and prove their point of view, argue with others, and convince others.

Today, the integrative approach involves solving educational tasks in a single step. Secondly, it is important that the collected material has a high

educational value, thus it is possible to form skills in students and in the process of developing skills, the teaching-learning method should be able to open the pedagogic framework of teaching basic needs.

IN CONCLUSION, in the case of technical higher education, it is very important to have a teacher's patience, to organize a quick conversation with students, and to create a comfortable environment for an independent exchange of ideas. In this case, it is important not to correct the mistake, but to encourage the student to express his opinion in clear language.

To date, in the field of higher education, the existing method of developing the educational and training environment is being used to study the needs of the students. The purpose and task of education are focused on the improvement of the individual's educational-teaching capacity and during the formation of his independent activity in the way of learning, the development of morally and esthetically mature students is considered an important goal.

On the basis of the science of human development, the essence of training is at a high level, that is, the development of skills and moral-ecstatic training is important, and it supports a mature trained person.

The main objective of teaching humanities in higher technical education is to educate the student ethically and aesthetically, and his attitude to the environment and his worldview are derived from the content of educational material and vocabulary. As an agent of mutual respect and cooperation in the school, it is a task that encourages the independent application of knowledge, skills, and abilities and ensures the transition to an independent form of activity. It is the most important requirement of today that the student's response to reading is carried out by the teacher as the organizer of the student's speech activity.

As a result of our analysis of the process of moral and ecstatic training of students of higher education through a foreign language, it was clarified as follows:

a) in the case of technical higher education, the practical requirements of the curriculum do not always respond to the needs of the time, that is, the practical, educational situation used in the curriculum is far from real life, and it is impossible to meet the needs of the students, it does not add anything to the development of concepts and the development of ideas;

b) the use of independent work at a staged level, which contributes to the improvement of moral and aesthetic education in the Japanese language, forms auditory and independent work skills, and is directed to expressing one's opinion and expressing a personal attitude to the main opinion;

c) the work of moral-aesthetic training should be subject to the situation from time to time and have a purpose-oriented approach.

Based on the above, we can say that in the next chapter of our research work, we will discuss the pedagogical aspects of moral and ecstatic training in the process of teaching students of technical higher education.

REFERENCES

1. Astin, Alexander W. and Helen S. Astin (1999). *Meaning and Spirituality in the Lives of College Faculty: A Study of Values, Authenticity, and Stress*. Los Angeles: Higher Education Research Institute.

2. Bazarova U.M. (2021). Improvement of mechanisms of moral and aesthetic education of students in foreign language lessons of a technical university. *Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities* 11(11)

3. Bazarova U.M. (2019) The Role of Spiritual and Moral Education of Students of Technical University in the Lessons of Foreign Languages. Philadelphia, USA (614-616).

4. Bazarova U.M. (2019). The state of the problem of moral and aesthetic education of students by means of a foreign language at the present stage. *International scientific journal "Scientific Horizons"* (1). Moscow

5. Bazarova U. (2022). Spiritual and moral education of students in the use of technology in the preparation of future professionals for innovative activities

in foreign language classes. *Архив научных исследований*, 2(1).

<http://journal.tsue.uz/index.php/archive/article/view/1812>

6. U.M.Bazarova, M.J.Ashirmatova, R.K.Alibekova (2022) The content and pedagogical conditions of moral and aesthetic education of the younger generation. // *International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education (INT-JECS)* ISSN: 1308-5581 Vol 14, Issue 03.

7. Bezugla, Marina. (2015). Formation in the student youth of spiritual and cultural values of education. (*Dissertation for a Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences*). *East-Ukrainian National University named after V. Dal*, Kyiv

8. Dalton, Jon C. (2001). Finding a Place for the Spirit in Work and the Community in The Implications of Student Spirituality for Student Affairs Practice, *Career and Calling*. (17-26)

9. Frankl, V. D.A. Leont'ev, M.P. Papush & E.V. Eydman. (1990) Man's Search for Meaning. *Translated from English and German*. Moscow.

10. Hakimova Muhabbat, Bazarova U.M., Mirzaeva M.N. Opportunities for Innovation Technologies in Higher Education. *International Journal on Integrated Education (IJIE)* Indonesia, 12/2020, 282 -285p.

11. Jablonski M, (2001). The Implications of Student Spirituality for Student